

Facial Features Monitoring for Real Time Drowsiness Detection using Support Vector Machine

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KEYWORDS

*Driver Fatigue,
Road Accidents,
Sleep Deprivation,
Fatigue Detection,
Alert System.*

ABSTRACT

Fatigue among drivers is a major cause of road accidents every year in India. Lack of sound sleep for six to eight hours is one of the primary reasons behind this fatigue. Drivers with sleep deprivation can imbalance the reaction time and decision making when behind the wheels and this can increase the cause of accidents. This type of accidents is more likely to result in death or severe injury as they tend to be in high speed and because of the fact that driver has fallen asleep cannot apply brake or skew to avoid or reduce the impact. Therefore, it is highly essential to create a smart system which can spot and alert the driver of his/her condition. Although there are few solutions proposed in this direction, most of them have not been implemented successfully and many of them only remain in theory. In this research paper, we propose an efficient driver fatigue detection and alert system using mainly open-source technologies. We implement and test this system in real time and the results are highly encouraging compared to many existing systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Driver fatigue, or drowsiness, contributes to many thousands of deaths and injuries on the roads every year. It has a role in up to 30% of fatal crashes and up to 15% of serious injuries [1]. Driver fatigue occurs when a driver does not get enough sleep or after long-distance driving. The influence of fatigue on driving safety is similar to that of alcohol impairment. A survey of the U.S

population found that 37% of workers got less than the recommended minimum of 7 h of sleep [2]. Driver fatigue is responsible for 22.7% of fatal accidents and 20.5% of accidents with injuries on Canadian roads. In 40% of fatigue-related accidents, the driver was awake for over 17 h [3]. The main problem with fatigue is that it is very difficult to be aware of the tiredness of drivers before they become too tired to drive safely. Driver

fatigue is a major cause of car accidents, since sleepy drivers are unable to make rapid decisions, and they may have slower reaction times [4]. Therefore, recent research also suggests that driver fatigue detection methodologies can be used to prevent such accidents [5]. The research on driver fatigue detection can be classified into two categories: passive driver monitoring system and active driver fatigue control system. Among them, the first is the use of preventive measures, by which a driver is monitored, and an alarm is displayed to advise the driver to stop the vehicle during the fatigue stage [5–7]. The second is the abnormal fatigue detection in which a driver is deemed to be asleep and the system can actively control the vehicle to avoid accidents [8–10]. In recent years, researchers have developed methodologies to detect or indicate the driver fatigue state prior to a collision [11–13]. Generally, data from three different sources have been used to classify driver fatigue or drowsiness. Firstly, vehicle-based measures are used to detect a drowsy or unsafe state. For example, vehicle-based measuring may be obtained by steering wheel angle, acceleration pedal data, and lane departure information by an external sensor [14,15]. Secondly, observation of the driver behavior method may be determined by continuous recording through a camera installed in the vehicle to monitor eye-closure time, eye blinking frequency, movement and pose of the head, and yawing, etc. [16–18]. The most recognized measure of these models is the percentage of eye closure time (PERCLOS) [19], although others have used measures such as eye aspect ratio (EAR) [20]. Thirdly, driver-based measures include physiological measurements such as electroencephalography (EEG), as well as heart rate, respiration rate, pulse pattern, and popular cortical signals, etc. [21–23]. In summary, owing to easy installation and low cost, observation of the driver behavior method has been widely used for fatigue detection. For example, attention technologies and smart eye technology employ the movement of the driver's eyes and position of the driver's head to determine the level of their fatigue [24,25]. In this study, we propose a real-time observation of the driver behavior method to detect driver fatigue. Our method only uses the inside vehicle camera, which is handy for the driver to carry on, or convenient to install in the vehicle. The novelty of this study is to develop a novel real-time driver fatigue detection system that has two major advantages. First,

we introduce a new face-tracking algorithm based on facial landmarks to improve detection accuracy. A tasks-constrained deep convolutional network is constructed to detect the face region based on 68 key points, which solve the optimization problem caused by different convergence speeds of each task. Second, we use K-nearest neighbor (KNN) to classify the state of the driver's eye. According to the real-time facial video images, the eye feature of eye aspect ratio (EAR), mouth aspect ratio (MAR), and percentage of eye closure time (PERCLOS) are calculated based on specific facial landmarks. Besides, the system proposes a comprehensive driver fatigue assessment model to assess the fatigue of drivers with eye/mouth feature selection to evaluate the level of driver fatigue.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Aishwarya et al. [1] have created a unique method that might effectively detect speeding on roadways and encourage drivers to obey traffic laws by driving below the posted speed limitations. The proposed system includes RFID (Radio Frequency Identification), which allows the average speed to be 2023 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communication and Applied Informatics (ACCAI) | 979-8-3503-1590-5/23/\$31.00 ©2023 IEEE | DOI: 10.1109/ACCAI58221.2023.10199888 calculated by measuring the time the vehicle needs to pass two consecutive readers, GSM (Global System for Mobile), which uses GSM technology to send the calculated speed and overspeed of the vehicle to the control room, and PIC (18F45K22). This method has delivered outcomes that are dependable, affordable, efficient, and timely. A reinforcement learning framework and a Kalman Filter that predicts positions were both supplied by Geist et al. [2]. The paper states that the issues of determining the precise location of bounding box in each frame for the stated item can be viewed as tracking the desired object inside the video material. By using video, Ginzburg et al. [3] created a technique for calculating the speed of autos. The created system has the following distinguishing characteristics: no accurate camera calibration is needed; minimal computing requirements for the computer evaluating the video sequence. This proposed system does not need to precisely detect the location of the camera in space, unlike other analogues. All that is needed is the camera suspension's measured height. The created system's ability to discern between the

movement of just the vehicle's license plates rather than the full vehicle is one of its useful features. The study uses a system to identify moving items in videos, classify them, keep track of them, and determine their average speed. The system's error rate is 5%. A system for vehicle speed detection from video streams was created by JozefGerat et al. [4] utilizing image processing techniques. It addresses the issue of vehicle speed detection using video record data and discusses the key techniques, including Gaussian mixture models, DBSCAN, Kalman filter, and optical flow. The architectural plan and a description of each segment's communication channels make up the implementation part. The conclusion includes testing of video recordings that were obtained utilizing various driving styles, vehicles, and vehicle positions at the recording. In order to overcome the object tracking issue, Kale et al. [5] combined a traditional optical-flow technique with motion vector estimates. Even without computing the quantitative characteristics, optical flow can provide important information about how an object moves. Motion vector estimation can be used to determine whether an object is present over multiple frames. This improves outcomes regardless of abnormalities like blurry images or busy backgrounds, which directly improves the algorithms' accuracy. A solid and dependable method for estimating vehicle speed was put out by Kassen N. et al. [6]. This provides the user with driving instructions and enables him to avoid being stuck in traffic. This strategy is RF-based. The generator of the radiofrequency current that is sent to the transmitting coil is a radiofrequency (RF) transmitter. In the frequency range from around 20 kHz to 300 GHz, radio frequency (RF) refers to the rate of oscillation of a magnetic, an alternating electric current or voltage, or of a mechanical system, or electromagnetic wave. Transmission rates range from 1 Kbps to 10 Kbps. An RF receiver, which uses the very similar frequency as the sender, receives the supplied data. In ordinary streets, this system has a speed estimation accuracy of 86% and a 78% average accuracy. A method to calculate the typical vehicle speed created for aerial video was put out by Ke et al. [7]. It tracks the object's movement between two succeeding frames using the optic flow method and the K-MEAN clustering algorithm. Using the data of the object's movement, the vehicle speed is calculated in picture scale before being translated to actual scale. and

the length of one frame. This approach has a 12% error rate. For target detection, Li et al. [8] use the features fusion method. In their research, features are extracted from various PIR sensors (which employ a pair of pyroelectric sensors) utilizing symbolic dynamic filtering (SDF) are subsequently categorized as targets or no-targets using several methods, including hierarchical agglomerative clustering, as K-means clustering, and spectral clustering. The literature extensively studies the classification of the PIR sensor readings using various machine learning methods. Because to their simplicity, the techniques support vector machines (SVM), K-nearest neighbors, and naive Bayes have drawn the attention of numerous academics. A machine learning strategy for object recognition that can analyze images very quickly and achieve greater detection capability than other strategies is described by Madasu et al. [9]. using digitized video taken with a stationary camera, to forecast traffic speed, the proposed method compares the vehicle position between the current frame and the previous frame. The camera device was calibrated using geometric equations. It demonstrated an overall accuracy of 83%. A brand-new vibration sensor device was put forward by Malik et al. [10], and it was mounted on the car. Vibration is activated in the event of a collision, and an infrared finder is used to locate the car. In order to retrieve the accident and find the culprit using a GPS locator, the incident was promptly documented to Patrol and Life Support. Researchers estimated vehicle speeds by incorporating accelerometer (measures vibration or acceleration of motion of a structure) readings over time and determining acceleration faults. Extensive testing was conducted to ensure that sensor speed is precise and strong in real-world driving environments. A method that uses a toolbox for image and video processing to determine vehicle speed was developed by Rad A. G. et al. [11]. Video sequences and photos with different resolutions might both be used by this system. A collection of workflow software and industry-standard algorithms for image analysis, evaluation, visualization, and algorithmic development is called the Image Processing Toolbox. In order to increase perspective vision and prepare the image for machine application, it is used to enhance visual input such as clarity, color, and brightness. An speed limit error of +7 km/h and -7 km/h was the outcome. Researchers Rangan P.R. et al. [12]

created an Automatic Speed Detection System to assess a vehicle's speed and, if over-speeding occurs, retrieve the specific vehicle's plate number, and mail it to the toll booth for a fee. The speed in this case is computed using the observable Doppler Effect. If excessive speed is estimated, a camera will take a photo of the car and employ. Using DIP (Digital Image Processing) methods, the license plate number is removed. Results demonstrated that the suggested designed system performs excellently, detects over-speeding vehicles, obtains the license number, and may be utilized to keep an eye out for them on roadways. A system to spot reckless driving on the highways and to notify the traffic authorities of any violations has been presented by Shabibi L. A. et al. [13] Many strategies demand human attention and involve numerous, difficult-to-implement tries. A buzzer, a control circuit, and an IR transmitter and receiver are required for the entire implementation. The voltage and resistivity of the photo-output diode vary proportionally to the quantity of IR light received. Some of the radiation that the IR transmitters emits is reflected back towards the Infrared sensor after the target is hit. With an IR Sender and IR Receiver, remote controllers are commonly used to remotely control electronic devices. If the car violates the traffic regulations, a buzzer sound alerts the police. For permanent magnet synchronous, Shedbalkar K. et al. [14] created a speed estimate method based on an enhanced Kalman filter. System is created using the SIMULINK model Blockset in MATLAB. A technique for solving the continuous form of Hidden Markov Models is the Kalman Filter. Latent variables are the subject of Hidden Markov. A Kalman filter is an algorithm that uses current position to forecast positions in the future. A method based on the optical flow method was developed by Shukla and Patel et al. [15] to identify the direction of object motion in video taken by a camera mounted above the road. Here, image processing is applied to all related frames as well as the generated displacement vectors. The center mass coordinates of each moving object are thus discovered. The gathered data is further examined before the estimated object motion is calculated. The height and tilt angle of the camera suspension must be determined prior to processing. The system determines the velocity of moving objects using computer vision technologies. This tactic has an 82% accuracy rate. In a sample movie, Wang

[16] developed a method for moving target recognition based on which the relationship between actual distance and expressed in terms of pixels. This technique for recognizing moving targets is quite trustworthy. To extract features from the moving automobiles in the video, the system used background and three-frame differencing. The vehicle centroid feature extraction technique was then used to track and position the vehicle.

3. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

Face location can be used to design a video camera system that tracks a person's face in a room. It plays a crucial role in intelligent vision systems and video surveillance. Despite extensive research in face segmentation, challenges remain due to variations in image complexity and application requirements.

This paper discusses a color analysis approach for face segmentation, including:

- Derivation of a universal model of human skin color
- Selection of an appropriate color space
- Overcoming limitations of color segmentation

3.1 Color Analysis

In recent years, color information has been increasingly utilized in the face-location problem, attracting significant attention. Several recent studies have explored this approach, highlighting its effectiveness. Typically, color information is employed for region segmentation rather than edge detection. Region segmentation can be broadly classified into two general approaches, as illustrated in Figure 1.

- **Image Partitioning Using Color Features:** This approach uses color as a key feature to divide an image into homogeneous regions.
- **Object Identification Using Color Features:** In this method, color is used to identify specific objects within an image. A notable application is the use of skin color to detect human faces. This is feasible because human skin exhibits a distinct color distribution that significantly differs—though not entirely—from background objects.

An example image is shown in figure 2. In another approach, the skin-color map can be designed using a histogramming technique on a given set of training

data. Therefore, this individual color feature can be defined by the presence of Cr values within the range of 136 to 156 and Cb values between 110 and 123. Using these value ranges, we successfully located the subject's face in another frame of Foreman and also in a different scene—a standard test image called Carphone—as shown in Figure 3. This approach was previously suggested by Li and Forchheimer; however, a detailed procedure for modeling individual color features and their choice of color space was not disclosed

Figure 1: Color information for region segmentation

Figure 2: Foreman image with white contour highlighting the facial region

Figure 3: Foreman and Carphone images, and their color segmentation results, obtained by using the same predefined skin-color map

3.2 Color Space

An image can be represented using various color space models. Some of the most commonly used models are:

- RGB (Red-Green-Blue)

This model represents the three primary colors—red, green, and blue. It is a hardware-oriented model widely used for color monitor displays.

- HSV (Hue-Saturation-Value)

HSV stands for Hue, Saturation, and Value.

- Hue describes the pure color attribute.
- Saturation defines the relative purity of the color or the amount of white light mixed with it.
- Value refers to the brightness of the image.

This model is commonly used in image analysis due to its intuitive representation of color.

- YCbCr (Luminance-Chrominance Model)

The YCbCr model is another hardware-oriented color space. Unlike the RGB model, it separates luminance (brightness) from chrominance (color information).

- Y represents the luminance (brightness) component.
- Cb and Cr, known as color difference signals, represent the chrominance components.
- Skin Color Segmentation in YCbCr Color Space

Skin color segmentation is applied in the YCbCr color space. To achieve this, the RGB color space is first converted to YCbCr using the following equations:

$$Y = 0.299R + 0.587G + 0.114B$$

$$Cb = (B - Y) \times 0.564 + 128$$

$$Cr = (R - Y) \times 0.713 + 128$$

Steps for Skin Color Segmentation

- Define the range for skin pixels in the YCbCr color space.
- Identify pixels (p) that fall within the specified range for the Cb and Cr components.
- Classify pixels as skin or non-skin pixels. Since the hand is a connected component made up of skin pixels, applying segmentation will isolate the hand from the background.

3.3 Edge Detection in Image Processing

Edges in an image are crucial features that provide valuable information for human perception. Edge detection refers to algorithms that identify points where image brightness changes sharply. Since edge detection generates large amounts of data, processing speed becomes a challenge. The primary objective of image processing is to enhance image quality for human interpretation or machine perception. This involves pixel-by-pixel processing, modification of pixel neighborhoods, and applying transformations to either the entire image or specific regions. To achieve real-time image processing, a hardware-level implementation is often required. Hardware-based solutions offer parallelism, significantly reducing processing time. MATLAB Simulink, a graphical interface-based tool, is used in this study due to its ease of use compared to other hardware description software.

Canny's Edge Detection Algorithm:

Figure 4: Block diagram of Canny's Edge Detection Algorithm

The block diagram of Canny's Edge Detection Algorithm is shown in figure 4.

The **Canny edge detection algorithm** is widely regarded as the **optimal edge detector**. John Canny developed this algorithm with the goal of improving existing edge detection techniques, and he successfully achieved this objective. His ideas and methods are detailed in his paper, "A Computational Approach to Edge Detection."

In his work, Canny established a set of criteria to enhance edge detection methods:

- **Low Error Rate** – Edges present in an image should not be missed, and there should be no false responses to non-edges.
- **Good Localization** – The detected edge points should be as close as possible to the actual edges in the image.
- **Single Response to an Edge** – A single edge should not produce multiple responses. This criterion ensures that the first two conditions alone do not lead to multiple detections of the same edge.

Steps in the Canny Edge Detection Algorithm:

Based on these principles, the Canny edge detector follows a series of steps:

- **Image Smoothing** – The image is first smoothed using a Gaussian filter to reduce noise.
- **Gradient Computation** – The gradient of the image is calculated to identify regions with high spatial derivatives, which indicate potential edges.
- **Non-Maximum Suppression** – The algorithm traces along the detected edges and suppresses any pixel that is not a local maximum, ensuring that only the most significant edge pixels remain.
- **Hysteresis Thresholding** – To finalize edge detection, the algorithm applies two threshold values:
 1. If the gradient magnitude is **below the lower threshold**, the pixel is suppressed (considered a non-edge).
 2. If the gradient magnitude is **above the higher threshold**, the pixel is classified as an edge.
 3. If the gradient magnitude falls **between the two thresholds**, the pixel is considered an edge only if it is

connected to a pixel with a gradient above the higher threshold.

Through this structured approach, the Canny edge detector effectively balances sensitivity to real edges while minimizing noise and false detections.

3.4 Sobel Filter Analysis

Filtering is the process of applying masks to images, where a mask is applied to an input image to produce an output image of the same size.

The filtering process involves **three steps of convolution**:

- **Mask Placement** – For each pixel in the input image, the mask is conceptually positioned over that pixel.
- **Weighted Multiplication** – Each pixel value under the mask is multiplied by its corresponding mask weight.
- **Summation and Assignment** – The resulting values are summed together to produce a single output value, which is then assigned to the corresponding pixel location in the output image.

The pixel values of the original image are shown in **Figure 5**. To compute the G_x and G_y gradients of the image, we perform convolution using **Sobel kernels** while applying **zero-padding** to extend the image boundaries.

The process of computing G_x and G_y using convolution and zero-padding is illustrated in **Figure 6**, while the resulting gradient images G_x and G_y are shown in **Figure 7**.

0	0	0	0	0
10	10	10	10	10
10	10	10	10	10
0	0	0	0	0
0	0	0	0	0

Figure 5: Pixel Values in the original image

-1	-2	-1	0	0	0
0	30	0x0	0	0	0
1	10x2	10x1	10	10	10
	10	10	10	10	10
	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0

1	0	-1			
2	-10	0x-2	0	0	0
1	10x0	10x-1	10	10	10
	10	10	10	10	10
	0	0	0	0	0
	0	0	0	0	0

Figure 6: The process of computing G_x and G_y

30	40	40	40	30
30	40	40	40	30
-30	-40	-40	-40	-30
-30	-40	-40	-40	-30
0	0	0	0	0

-10	0	0	0	10
-30	0	0	0	30
-30	0	0	0	30
-10	0	0	0	10
0	0	0	0	0

Figure 7: The Gradients G_x and G_y

4. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

The following figures present the results of the proposed approach.

Figure 8: Capturing the Face

Figure 9: Fatigue of face (drowziness)

Figure 10: Non-fatigue of face (undrowziness)

4.CONCLUSIONS

A speed detection camera system has been developed to measure the speed of vehicles on the highways. The proposed system is capable to identify target vehicles in the presence of partial occlusions and ambiguous poses, and the cluttered background. The proposed method is capable to detect multiple vehicles simultaneously by drawing the surrounding bounding box. Experimental results show that the proposed model gives relatively good performance. The accuracy of counting vehicles is 94%, although the vehicle detection

was 100% in the presence of partial occlusions. The proposed method has a limitation that it fails when two vehicles are merged together and system treat them as a single entity. The future work will focus to overcome this limitation and to estimate speed on real-time live video sequences.

Conflict of interest statement

Authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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